

A STUDY ON ISSUES AND CHALLENGES OF HANDLOOM WEAVER IN KONGU REGION OF TAMILNADU

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Abstract:

Handloom industry in India is the most important & ancient cottage industry with a decentralized setup. The industry is providing livelihood for millions of people in the country. About ten millions are directly depend on the industry to eke out their livelihood. While many more millions of people depend upon subsidiary, occupations connected with the handloom industry. The share of employment provided by the handloom industry in the total decentralized sector is above 5.5%. Thus, this industry constitutes one of the major sectors providing employment to the large number of people next only to agriculture. In regards to production of cloth, this handloom industry is producing one third of the total cloth requirement of the country.

Kongu Region:

From time immemorial, Kongunadu has been in existence as "The home of Tamilians". The history of Kongunadu dates back to the 8th century AD. The name Kongunadu originated from the term "Kongu", meaning nectar or honey. Kongu came to be called as Kongunadu with the growth of civilization. The ancient Kongunadu country was made up of various districts and taluks which are currently known as Palani, Dharapuram, Karur, Nammakkal, Thiruchengodu, Erode, Salem, Dharmapuri, Satyamangalam, Nilgiris, Avinashi, Coimbatore, Pollachi and Udumalpet. The Kongu region flourishes mainly due to their extreme hard work, commitment, objective nature and innovation in their respective fields. Kongu Nadu has the highest urban proportion in the Tamil Nadu state and contributes 2/3 of the Tamil Nadu's state revenue. But this is often ignored by the government. The Gounders are an influential community in Coimbatore, Nilgiris, Karur, Tiruchirappalli, Namakkal, Erode, Tiruppur, Salem, Krishnagiri, Dharmapuri and Dindigul districts. A good section of the community is highly educated, many from the US and UK. Most of them are third-generation businessmen and put together, they generate roughly Rs 40,000 crore of export revenue annually. Through sheer hard work, its members have attained international recognition. They figure among the global leaders in several sectors including grey cotton, home textiles, hosiery, industrial and automobile components, heavy vehicles and even turmeric.

Issues and Challenges of Handloom Weavers:

Business world is highly competitive for any sector and they have to face so many problems. The handloom weavers societies are no exception to this Weavers co-operative societies are established with the objective of improving the economic conditions of the poor weavers. In this modern world of technological advancement, the societies face various problems in many fields like production, marketing and finance. The problems are -

- ✓ Lack of Finance.
- ✓ Inadequate supply of yarn by Co-optex.
- ✓ Supply of inferior quality of yarn.
- ✓ Competition from master weavers and powerloom owners.
- ✓ Lack of improvement in the modernisation of looms.
- ✓ Non-utilisation of multichannel marketing.
- ✓ Absence of innovative designs and combination of colors.
- ✓ Absence of timely decisions to cope up with the prevailing circumstances.
- ✓ Disloyalty of weaver members.
- ✓ Lack of competition among the weavers co-operative societies.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the overview of handloom industry.
- ✓ To assess the social and economic conditions of the handloom weavers in the Kongu region of Tamilnadu.
- ✓ To enlist various raw materials related problems faced by handloom weavers.
- ✓ To enlist marketing related problems faced by handloom weavers.

- ✓ To enquire about the employment opportunity of handloom weavers.
- ✓ To analyze consumer behavior towards handloom products.

Area of Study:

No of Loom & Family Engaged in Production:

Year: 2013-2014

S.No	Name of the districts	No. of family engaged in	
		Handloom	Power loom
1	Coimbatore, Erode and Tirupur	35232	7942

Source: Asst. Director of Handlooms, Coimbatore & Erode.

Sampling Techniques:

The Study use descriptive research design to conduct the research. Among 35232 populations the study conducted with 450 respondents from this three area (Coimbatore, Tirupur & Erode). Questionnaire has been collected randomly from the total population through friends and relatives.

Collection of Data:

For the study the Primary data was collected from 450 respondents by supplying the questionnaire and through direct interview method. Secondary data are those data which are already collected by some agency, through books, magazines and through internet for some other purpose. The data collected during the project on which the information where derived from so many sources.

Primary Data:

They are predominantly collected from the survey instrument the questionnaire contained qualitative data as well as quantitative data. Some questions were closed ended and some others were close ended for these study 450 respondents were selected. The researcher personally questioned all these respondents.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data for the study collected from the published and unpublished sources annual reports, research, journals and various related website.

Limitations of the Study:

The present study is subject to the following limitations:

- ✓ The study is restricted to kongu region alone.
- ✓ The time frame allowed for the study is a very short period, thus the sample size has been restricted.
- ✓ The sample was confined to handloom weavers alone.
- ✓ The findings of the study cannot be generalized to other industries.

Simple Percentage:

Sales and Marketing Issues:

S.No	Sales and Marketing Issues	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Effort needs to promote sales	Exhibitions	252	56%
		Publicity	107	24%
		Improving Artistic Value	24	5%
		Improving function value	20	4%
		No Effort	47	11%
		Total	450	100%
2	Making promotional activities	Yes	229	51%
		No	221	49%
		Total	450	100%
3	Type of Promotional activity	Personal selling	81	35%
		Shore room display	44	19%
		Tele media ad	14	6%
		Print media ad	90	40%
		Total	229	100%
4	Providing any discounts	Yes	342	76%
		No	108	24%
		Total	450	100%
5	Percentage of discounts	1%-10%	214	63%
		11%-20%	77	23%
		21%-30%	32	9%
		31%-40%	11	3%
		More than 40%	8	2%
		Total	342	100%
6	Demand for the product	Festival	223	50%

		Aadi Rebate	179	39.7%
		School & College Time	46	10%
		Others	2	0.3%
		Total	450	100%
7	Facing excess demand	Increase Production	91	20%
		Purchase Outside	184	41%
		Not Possible	175	39%
		Total	450	100%
8	Problem in marketing	No demand	141	31%
		No remuneration	115	26%
		High transport cost	46	10%
		High competition	148	33%
		Total	450	100%

Inference:

Effort Needs to Promote Sales: The above table shows that 56% of the respondents says that they promote sales through exhibitions. 24% of the respondents are using publicity. 5% of the respondents like to improve the sales through Artistic value. 4% of the respondents like to improve the sales through future value and 11% of the respondents not doing any effort to promote sales.

Making Promotional Activity: The above table shows that 51% of the respondents will make promotional activity and 49% of the respondents did not make any promotional activity.

Type of Promotional Activity: The above table shows that 35% of the respondents using personal selling for promotion. 19% of the respondents using Show room display for promotion. 6% of the respondents use Tele media ad and 40% of the respondents using print media ad for promotion.

Providing any Discounts: The above table shows that 76% of the respondents provide discounts and 24% of the respondents not providing any discounts.

Percentage of Discounts: The table shows that 63% of the respondents provide discounts up to 1%-10%. 23% of the respondents provide discounts up to 11%-20%. 9% of the respondents provide discounts up to 21%-30%. 3% of the respondents provide discounts up to 31%-40% and 2% of the respondents provide discounts more than 40%.

Demand for the Product: 50% of the respondents say that during festival time they have high demand. 39.7% of the respondents say that demand arise in Aadi rebate. 10% of the respondents says that demand arise during school and college time and 0.3% of the respondents says that demand arises in other time.

Facing Excess Demand: 20% of the respondents face the demand by increasing the production. 41% of the respondents face the demand by getting the product from outside and 39% of the respondents says they are notable to face demand.

Problem in Marketing: The above table shows that 31% there is No demand for the products. 26% of the respondents say there is no remuneration. 10% of the respondents say that there is high transportation cost and 33% of the respondents say that there is high competition.

Consumer Behavior:

S.No	Consumer Behavior	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Age group of customer	20 - 25 Years	37	8%
		26 - 35 Years	61	14%
		36 - 40 Years	65	14%
		41 - 45 Years	112	25%
		46 - 50 Years	85	19%
		Over 51 Years	90	20%
		Total	450	100%
2	Criteria that affects the customer to buy	Price	54	12%
		Quality	94	21%
		Design	188	42%
		Colors	114	25%
		Total	450	100%
3	Problem faced with the customer at the time of sales	Style	106	23%
		Unique	121	27%
		Low price	121	27%
		More work	102	23%
		Total	450	100%

Inference:

Age Group of the Customer: The above table shows that 8% of the respondents are belonging to the age group of 20-25 years.14% of the respondents are belonging to the age group of 26-35 years.14% of the respondents are belonging to the age group of 36-40 years.25% of the respondents are belonging to the age group of 41-45 years.19% of the respondents are belonging to the age group of 45-50 years. 20% of the respondents are belonging to the age group of above 50 years.

Criteria that Affect the Customer to Buy: The above table shows that 12% of the respondents buy the product on the basis of price. 21% of the respondents buy the product on the basis quality.42% of the respondents buy the product on the basis design. 25% of the respondents buy the product on the basis color.

Problem Faced with the Customer at the Time of Sales: The above table shows that 23% of the respondents say that the customer focused only on style. 27% of the respondents say that the customer focused only on unique design.27% of the respondents say that the customer focused only on low price.23% of the respondents say that the customer focused only on more work.

Chi-Square Test:

Sex with Nature of Weavers:

Aim: To find out the significant relationship between Sex and Nature of Weavers

Testing Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant relationship between Sex and Nature of Weavers

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is significant relationship between Sex and Nature of Weavers

Particulars	Individual	Master	Co-operative	Total
Female	60	47	54	161
Male	90	103	96	289
Total	150	150	150	450

Chi-Square:

Particulars		Nature of Weavers			Total	
		Individual	Master	Co-operative		
Sex	Female	Count	60	47	54	161
		Expected Count	53.6	53.6	53.6	161
		% within Sex	37.26%	29.19%	33.5%	100%
	Male	Count	90	103	96	289
		Expected Count	96.3	96.3	96.3	289
		% within Sex	31.14%	31.14%	31.14%	100%
Total	Count	150	150	150	450	
	Expected Count	150	150	150	450	
	% within Sex	33.3%	33.3%	33.3%	100%	

Chi-Square Test Result:

Level of Significance	Degrees of freedom	Chi-square value
5%	2	2.455

Inference: Using Chi-square Test a null hypothesis that H₀ : Sex is independent of the nature of weavers against the alternative hypothesis that H₁ : Sex depends on the nature of weavers. The Chi-square test gave the calculated chi-square value 2.455. Since, this value is less than the critical value 5.99 for 2 degrees of freedom (referred from chi-square table) we have to accept the null hypothesis. ie., There no significant relationship between Sex and Nature of Weavers.

Procurement of Raw Material with Nature of Weavers:

Aim: To find out the significant relationship between procurement of raw material and Nature of Weavers

Testing Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant relationship between procurement of raw material and Nature of Weavers

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is significant relationship between procurement of raw material and Nature of Weavers

Particulars	Individual	Master	Co-operative	Total
Price	55	32	63	150
Quality	32	68	42	142
Quantity	33	24	11	68
Availability	30	26	34	90
Total	150	150	150	450

Chi-Square:

Particulars	Nature of Weavers			Total
	Individual	Master	Co-operative	

Procurement of raw material	Price	Count	55	32	63	150
		Expected Count	50	50	50	150
		% within Sex	36.6%	21.4%	42%	100%
	Quality	Count	32	68	42	142
		Expected Count	47.3	47.3	47.3	142
		% within Sex	22.5%	47.8%	29.5%	100%
	Quantity	Count	33	24	11	68
		Expected Count	22.6	22.6	22.6	68
		% within Sex	48.5%	35.3%	16.2%	100%
	Availability	Count	30	26	34	90
		Expected Count	30	30	30	90
		% within Sex	33.3%	28.8%	37.7%	100%
Total	Count	150	150	150	450	
	Expected Count	150	150	150	450	
	% within Sex	33.3%	33.3%	33.3%	100%	

Chi-Square Test Result:

Level of Significance	Degrees of freedom	Chi-square value
5%	6	36.91

Inference: Using Chi-square Test a null hypothesis that H_0 : Procurement of raw material is independent of the nature of weaver against the alternative hypothesis that H_1 : Procurement of raw material depends on the nature of weavers. The Chi-square test gave the calculated chi-square value 36.91. Since, this value is greater than the critical value 12.592 for 6 degrees of freedom (referred from chi-square table) we have to reject the null hypothesis. i.e., There no significant relationship between Procurement of raw material and Nature of Weavers.

Suggestions:

Textile industry is one of the major industries in India. It provides more revenue to our country. Now a day it becomes sick industry in our country. Textile industry is the only source of supplying raw material for handloom industry. The individual weavers and co-operative weavers are not able to buy the raw material at high price so they are depending of co-operative society. The society gets the raw material from textile mills and yarn traders. The price of the yarn is too high because of low production (yarn) and the quality is not up to the mark. The weavers are not procuring the raw material on the basis of quality but on the basis of price of the yarn. So the quality of the product also not up to the expectation. Government should take necessary step to bring back the textile industry to help the weavers.

Conclusion:

The handloom industry is the most challenging one in India. Particularly in Kongu region we can find more number of weavers is male between the age group of 31-35 years. Very Few incomes are earned by the weavers. Handloom sarees are popular in India. There is no promotional for selling the product other than personal selling. Demand of the product is more only during festival time. Discount sales attract the customers. The market is highly competitive. The procurement of raw material is a challenging one and most of the weavers procure raw material from Co-operative society. In Present days educated peoples are moving to other sectors. So the handloom sectors are in depression stage.

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